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My Cross-dresser Father

My father is a farmer,
Sharp bolo in his hands:
Tills the earth,
Carabao by his side,
Sometimes a fisherman,
Swam the river placing traps.

In the eve of September 27,
He wore baro, saya, and pañuelo.
He led us to take refuge in the mountains.

It was 1901.
He kept his bolo inside his saya,
Not to be seen by white men.
With fear and chaos,
We fled to the mountains,
Amidst the turmoil.